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Research Article

**EVALUATION OF ANTIHYPERLIPIDEMIC ACTIVITY OF
POLYHERBAL FORMULATION IN CAFETERIA DIET
INDUCED HYPERLIPIDEMIC RAT MODEL**

Anitha Nandagopal*, Adeeba Husna, Anupama Koneru

Department of Pharmacology, Sultan- ul -Uloom College of Pharmacy, Mount Pleasant # 8-2-249, Road no.3 Banjara Hills, Hyderabad-500 034, Telangana, India.

Article Received: October 2019 **Accepted:** November 2019 **Published:** December 2019**Abstract:**

The purpose of the present study is to elucidate the antihyperlipidemic activity of the polyherbal formulation of methanolic extract of Moringa olifera leaves, Trachyspermum ammi seeds and Mimosa pudica leaves (MMTM) in cafeteria diet induced hyperlipidemic rats. The rats were given a high fat diet called Cafeteria diet to induce hyperlipidemia for 21 days. The extraction for the polyherbal formulation was done by methanol using Soxhlet apparatus. The phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of flavanoids, steroids, phenols and tannins. The administration of the MMTM formulation resulted in decrease in the body weights of the hyperlipidemic rats when compared with the disease control. Treatment with MMTM 200mg/kg and 400mg/kg significantly decreased TC, TG, LDL and increased HDL levels. The histopathological results also revealed normal hepatocytes in the MMTM treated group. Hence it may be concluded that antihyperlipidemic activity of the MMTM extract may be due to the presence of phytochemical constituents such as flavanoids, steroids, phenolic compounds and tannins.

Key words: Cafeteria diet, Trachyspermum ammi, Mimosa pudica, Moringa olifera, Hyperlipidemia.

Corresponding author:**Dr. N. Anitha,**

Professor and HOD,

Dept. of Pharmacology,

Sultan- ul -Uloom College of Pharmacy, Mount Pleasant # 8-2-249,

Road no.3, Banjara Hills, Hyderabad-500 034, Telangana, India.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hyperlipidemia is characterized by elevated levels of the plasma lipids. This includes cholesterol, cholesterol esters, triglycerides, phospholipids and plasma lipoproteins like very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL), low density lipoprotein (LDL) and high-density lipoprotein (HDL) [1]. Hyperlipidemia relates to raised oxidative stress inflicting vital production of oxygen free radicals which causes oxidative modifications in low density lipoproteins. This results in the commencement and development of atherosclerosis and related cardio vascular diseases [2]. Therefore, it is treated in patients to lower the risk of ischemic heart disease, cardiovascular or cerebro vascular diseases [3].

Antihyperlipidemic drugs are usually taken into consideration to treat hyperlipidemia among which statins are most commonly used with the price of severe side effects such as arrhythmias, fatigue, pneumonia and gall bladder stone. Therefore, to minimize the side effects caused by the allopathic drugs it is advisable to use natural products. These herbal medicines are used since ancient times for healing several diseases with less or no side effects [4]. Therefore, in this study, to evaluate antihyperlipidemic activity, polyherbal formulation consisting of *Moringa olifera*-leaves, *Trachyspermum ammi*-seeds and *Mimosa pudica*-leaves was used.

Moringa olifera belonging to the family Moringaceae is often called drumstick that possesses numerous organic and medicinal values attributed to its roots, bark, leaves, flowers fruits and seeds [5]. Information revealed that almost all the parts of the plant possess antimicrobial [6], hepatoprotective [7], antidiabetic [8] and cardiac stimulation properties [9].

Trachyspermum ammi belonging to the family Apeaceae is commonly called as Ajwain. This is rich in niacin and thymol which have properties to maintain the heart in healthy condition. It also has properties that enhance nerve impulse and circulation within the heart [10-13]. *Mimosa pudica* of the family Mimosaceae is a creeping annual herb grown throughout the India [14]. It holds properties such as anticonvulsant, antimicrobial, analgesic, antidiarrheal, antiulcer and antimalarial [15].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Collection and extraction of plant material

The whole dried seeds of *Trachyspermum ammi*, dried leaves of *Moringa olifera* and dried leaves of *Mimosa pudica* were procured and authenticated from Dr. Shaik Mohammed Aliuddin, Secretary of Hyderabad Unani Research Foundation, Hyderabad, Telangana State. The above substances were then grounded into coarse powder and were extracted with methanol using Soxhlet apparatus.

Preparation of methanolic extracts of poly herbal formulation

About 300 gms mixture of *Moringa olifera* leaves, *Trachyspermum ammi* seeds and *Mimosa pudica* leaves at the ratio of 1:1:1 were extracted by Soxhlet with 1000 ml of methanol (MMTM) for about 18 hrs. The MMTM extract was then subjected to dryness at room temperature.

Phytochemical analysis

The MMTM extract was subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening to determine the type of phytoconstituents present.

Animals

Albino wistar rats of either sex (100-150gm) were purchased from Sainath agencies, Musheerabad, Hyderabad, India. Animals were kept under standard well controlled laboratory conditions and experiments were performed in the morning according to current guidelines for the care of laboratory animals and ethical guidelines for the investigation in conscious animals. The experimental protocol was given approval by Institutional Animal Ethics Committee and was carried under the compliance of IAEC guidelines (IAEC/SUCP/ 2019/01).

Cafeteria Diet

Hyperlipidemia in the rats was induced by cafeteria diet (CD). The CD consisted of three diets, namely 40g of condensed milk plus 40g of bread, 15g chocolate plus 30g of biscuit plus 30g dried coconut and 40g cheese plus 50g boiled potatoes.

Experimental design

Wistar Albino rats of either sex were randomly divided into 5 groups each consisting of 6.

Group 1 (Normal control): This group will be given pellet chow and vehicle (0.5% w/v CMC, p.o.) for about 21 days.

Group 2 (Disease control): This group will be given CD + 0.5% w/v CMC by p.o for about 21 days.

Group 3 (Standard): This group will be given CD + Atorvastatin 30mg/kg BW in 0.5% w/v CMC by p.o for about 21 days.

Group 4 (MMTM 200mg/kg): This group will be given CD + MMTM 200mg/kg BW in 0.5% w/v CMC by p.o for about 21 days.

Group 5 (MMTM 400mg/kg): This group will be given CD + MMTM 400mg/kg BW in 0.5% w/v CMC by p.o for about 21 days.

Collection of blood and biochemical analysis

On 7th, 14th and 21st day, 2hrs after drug treatment, blood samples were collected from retro-orbital plexus under mild ether anesthesia. This blood samples were then centrifuged for about 10 mins. The serum was isolated and assayed for biochemical parameters like TC, TG, LDL and HDL using standard protocol method.

Histopathological study

On 21st day, the animals were sacrificed by cervical dislocation and liver was excised. The liver was transferred to 10% formalin solution for fixation. After the fixation of the tissue it was embedded in paraffin wax. The tissue was serially sectioned (3-5 μ m) and stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin for assessment of histopathological changes in liver tissue.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis was carried out using Graph pad prism 8.2.0. All results were expressed as Mean \pm SEM. Groups of data were compared with analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Dunnet's multiple comparison test to identify significance ($p < 0.001$, $p < 0.01$, $p < 0.05$) among groups.

RESULTS:

Preliminary Phytochemical Investigation

The qualitative analysis of the phytochemical constituents of the MMTM extract revealed the presence of flavonoids, steroids, phenols and tannins.

Body weights

The body weights were recorded on day 0, day 7, day 14 and day 21. There was decrease in the body weights of the MMTM 200mg/kg and 400mg/kg treated groups (140 g) and (136 g) when compared with the disease control (230 g). The reductions in body weights of the MMTM groups were similar to that of standard group (130 g). The MMTM 400mg/kg showed more reduction in weight when compared with MMTM 200mg/kg were shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Effect of MMTM on the body weights of the experimental animals

The data were analyzed by one way ANOVA followed by dunnet's multiple comparison tests. The values were expressed as Mean \pm SEM. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$ when compared with disease control group. ### $p < 0.001$ when compared with vehicle control group.

Total Cholesterol

The total cholesterol was recorded for three weeks. There was decrease in the cholesterol levels of the MMTM 200 mg/kg and 400mg/kg treated groups (150 mg/dL) and (145 mg/dL) when compared with the disease control (240 mg/dL). The results of the MMTM treated groups were very much closer to that of the standard group (135 mg/dL). The higher dose showed more reduction when compared with the lower dose (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Effect of MMTM on the Total Cholesterol of the experimental animals

The data were analyzed by one way ANOVA followed by dunnet's multiple comparison tests. The values were expressed as Mean \pm SEM. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $P < 0.01$, * $P < 0.05$ when compared with disease control group. ### $P < 0.001$ when compared with vehicle control group.

Triglycerides

MMTM 200 mg/kg and 400mg/kg treated groups significantly reduced the levels of triglycerides i.e., (100mg/dL) and (97.5mg/dL) when compared with the disease control (180mg/dL). The results of the MMTM treated groups were quite similar to that of the standard group (94.7mg/dL). MMTM 400mg/kg was found to be more effective (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Effect of MMTM on the Triglycerides of the experimental animals

The data were analyzed by one way ANOVA followed by dunnet's multiple comparison test. The values were expressed as Mean \pm SEM. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $P < 0.01$, * $P < 0.05$ when compared with disease control group. ### $P < 0.001$ when compared with vehicle control group.

LDL

Disease control group showed increase in LDL levels i.e., (77.3mg/dL) whereas MMTM 200mg/kg and 400mg/kg treated groups showed reduction in LDL levels which was found to be (45mg/dL) and (42.5mg/dL) respectively. The results of the MMTM treated groups were quite similar to that of the standard group (40mg/dL). MMTM 400mg/kg was found to be more effective (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Effect of MMTM on the LDL Cholesterol of the experimental animals

The data were analyzed by one way ANOVA followed by dunnet's multiple comparison test. The values were expressed as Mean \pm SEM. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $P < 0.01$, * $P < 0.05$ when compared with disease control group. ### $P < 0.001$ when compared with vehicle control group.

HDL

There was increase in the HDL levels of MMTM 200mg/kg and 400 mg/kg treated groups (35 mg/dL) and (36.2 mg/dL) respectively. However there was decrease in HDL levels of disease control group which was found to be (22 mg/dL). The results of the MMTM treated groups were quite similar to that of the standard group i.e., (38mg/dL). The higher dose of the MMTM extract was found to be more effective when compared to lower dose (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Effect of MMTM on the HDL Cholesterol of the experimental animals

The data were analyzed by one way ANOVA followed by dunnet's multiple comparison test. The values were expressed as Mean \pm SEM. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $P < 0.01$, * $P < 0.05$ when compared with disease control group. ### $P < 0.001$ when compared with vehicle control group.

Histopathology

The liver of the normal control group rats showed normal hepatocytes in the portal, periportal and central lobular region as shown in the Figure 6A. The liver of the disease control group revealed the presence of multifocal necrosis in the hepatocytes of portal and periportal region as shown in the Figure 6B. Whereas the liver of the standard group showed no signs of inflammation and necrosis and also the hepatocytes appeared to be normal. This is shown by the arrow in the Figure 6C. As pointed by the arrows in the Figure 6D the hepatocytes appeared normal in the portal, periportal and centrilobular region of the MMTM 200mg/kg treated group and also mild sinusoidal hemorrhages were noticed. Hepatocytes in the portal and periportal region of the liver were seen normal in the MMTM 400mg/kg which is shown by the arrows in the Figure 6E.

Figure 6A: Normal control

Figure 6B: Disease control

Figure 6C: Standard control

Figure 6D: MMTM 200mg/kg

Figure 6E: MMTM 400mg/kg

Figure 6: Effect of MMTM extracts 200mg/kg and 400mg/kg on cafeteria diet induced hyperlipidemic rats

DISCUSSION:

Cardiovascular diseases are known to be the leading cause of death mostly in industrialized nations. WHO reported coronary artery disease to be the fifth for the leading cause of death in the year 1990 which were estimated to top the list with the levels of high density lipoprotein cholesterol which is closely related to coronary artery disease and atherosclerosis. This indicates that hyperlipidemia is majorly responsible for health problems worldwide mostly coronary artery disease. Hyperlipidemia damages various tissues which alters the cell function causing cell damage and other pathological conditions.

Antihyperlipidemic drugs are most commonly used for the treatment of hyperlipidemia among which

Statins are believed to be the most efficient and best tolerated drug in reducing the levels of lipids and lipoproteins but all these agents are associated with adverse effects. Since herbal therapy is a holistic therapy, the use of herbal plants is assumed to be safe as the drugs do not generally involve adverse effects.

In the present study we are using a polyherbal formulation to screen the antihyperlipidemic effect. The methanolic extract of the polyherbal formulation MMTM was used to treat cafeteria diet induced hyperlipidemic rat models. Upon literature survey it was concluded that these herbal plants possess active constituents such as flavonoids, phenolic compounds, steroids, alkaloids and glycosides. The rats were given

a high fat diet called Cafeteria diet to induce hyperlipidemia for 21 days.

Increase in fat intake results in body weight gain was revealed by the study conducted on humans. Thus, the current study proved the increase in body weight of the animals when they were fed with the cafeteria diet for 21 days. However, there was reduction in body weight of the animals treated with MMTM 200mg/kg and 400mg/kg which resembled the reduction of body weights treated with standard drug. The group MMTM 400mg/kg showed more similarity to the standard. This was in accordance with the study conducted by Ghasi et.al [16].

In the current study treatment with MMTM 200mg/kg and 400mg/kg significantly reversed the abnormally increased TC, TG, and LDL and decreased HDL levels. MMTM 400mg/kg was found to be more effective when compared with MMTM 200mg/kg. This resembled the study conducted by Mehta et.al [17]. The study conducted by Ijaz.J et.al [18] to evaluate antihyperlipidemic efficacy of Ajwain also showed the similar results as that of the present study with the MMTM.

The histopathological results indicated that disease control group showed multifocal necrosis in the hepatocytes of portal and periportal region and peribiliary inflammation in the hepatocytes of the liver. The hepatocytes of the liver in the MMTM 200mg/kg and 400mg/kg were found to be normal and there was mild haemorrhage noticed in the MMTM 200mg/kg treated group. This reveals that MMTM 400mg/kg treated group was more effective and showed significant antihyperlipidemic effect with that of the standard drug. This was similar to that of study conducted by Poovathumkal J.N.et.al [19].

CONCLUSION:

To sum up, the antihyperlipidemic effect of MMTM extract was studied in experimental animals. The administration of the MMTM formulation resulted in decrease in the body weights of the hyperlipidemic rats when compared with the disease control. Also it was seen that upon administration of MMTM (200mg) and (400mg) to the hyperlipidemic rats there was reduction in TC, TG, LDL and increase in HDL levels. The histopathological results also indicated the protective effect of the MMTM extract as the hepatocytes of the liver seemed to be normal in the MMTM treated group. From the results it may be concluded that the antihyperlipidemic effect of the MMTM extract could be due to the presence of phytochemical constituents such as flavonoids,

steroids, phenolic compounds and tannins. Further studies are needed to isolate the fractions of phytochemical constituents and explore its molecular mechanism.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest among the authors.

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